

Anatomy on Leaf Blade of *Eleusine indica* L. (Gramineae): A Study on Kranz Grass

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Received date: July 02, 2020 Accepted date: Dec. 08, 2020</p>	<p>The anatomical features of <i>Eleusine indica</i> L. belonging to Gramineae family were investigated in the present study which was conducted in the laboratory of Crop Botany, EXIM Bank Agricultural University Bangladesh, Chapainawabganj. The leaf blades of field grown healthy plants were studied. Leaf blade surface was examined around stained peeling. Anatomical features were observed in transverse sections stained with 1% aqueous solution of safranin under a light microscope. Different types of cells diagram were measured from the photographs. Stomata were present in both abaxial and adxial surfaces of the leaf of <i>E. indica</i> L., therefore, the leaf is amphistomatic. In <i>E. indica</i> L. presence of cork cells, micro hair, long and short cells with sinuous wall showed various defensive activities against disease and environmental stress. In the features of ventral surface of leaf blade, long longitudinal veins, small longitudinal veins and transverse veins were observed. Ligule located at the junction of leaf blade and leaf sheath where ligule hairs existed profusely. Upper and lower epidermis layers were made of elongated compact cells. In the upper layer, large bulliform cells (85.68 µm in average diameter) and small bulliform cells (31.02µm in average diameter) were observed. They were arranged in cluster. Between the two epidermal layers, a chlorophyllus mesophyll layer was compactly arranged but it was not differentiated from palisade and spongy parenchyma. A layer of mesophyll cell is present surrounding the bundle sheath cell in ring like fashion. Average diameter of mesophyll cell was measured 40.49 µm and number of mesophyll cells was two between vascular bundles. Two types of vascular bundle, large and small were attended alternately. The vascular bundles of the leaf blade were associated with strands of hypodermal sclerenchyma. Bundle sheath cells were located surround vascular bundle and contain chloroplasts and small starch grains. The features of vascular bundle, sheath cells and mesophyll cells reveal kranz anatomy, therefore, the experimented plant (<i>Eleusine indica</i> L.) was suggested to be a C₄ plants. The epidermal features of the plant studied will help to resolve taxonomic problems.</p>

Key words: Anatomical, *Eleusine indica*, Goosegrass, Kranz anatomy, Leaf blades

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1. INTRODUCTION

Goosegrass, *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. is an annual or short-lived perennial pantropical grass that is mostly considered as a noxious weed (Jalaluddin et al., 2010). Grass branches from the base and can have erection, decumbent or prostrate habit. The leaves are alternate and the leaf-blade is flat, linear and sometimes folded (Welsh, 1998; Holm et al., 1977; Stone, 1970). The spikelet is oppressed, disposed in two rows on a single side of the rachis (FAO, 2017). The root system is particularly tough and difficult to pull out (Ecocrop, 2019).

Eleusine indica L. is a pantropical and subtropical grass. The geographical origin of *E. indica* is uncertain but it is considered native to Africa and temperate and tropical Asia. Now it is distributed almost throughout the tropical world and extends significantly into the sub-tropics, especially in North America, Europe and Africa. It is found in the waste places, along roadsides and riversides, beaches and open banks and in damp marshlands. It thrives on sandy soil and N-rich soils. It is a threat in arable land, in lawns and in plantations and nurseries (Swarbrick, 1997). Goose grass is a summer plant and it is a fast-growing grass that optimally grows in full sunlight. It withstands some dry periods with its extensive root system. It can grow on very shallow or compacted soils (Wagner et al., 1999).

Eleusine indica L. is resistant to herbicides (Doll, 2000; Mueller et al., 2011; Vargas et al., 2013; Jalaludin et al., 2010; Jing et al., 2014; San et al., 2014).

Eleusine indica L. can be used as forage. It is palatable to livestock when young but becomes tough at later stages. It can be made into coarse hay or silage. The seedlings can be eaten raw or cooked as vegetables and the seeds can be cooked whole or ground into flour in times of scarcity in India (Ecocrop, 2019). In ethnoveterinary medicine, goose grass is used to treat fever in ruminants (Pattanayak et al., 2017). *Eleusine indica* L. is used as a local medicinal plant with antioxidant (Iqbal & Gnanaraj, 2012; Sagnia et al., 2014), antimicrobial (Sagnia et al., 2014) and anticancer (Amarpreet, 2014; Hansakul, 2009) properties. The whole plant, especially the root, is depurative, diuretic, anti-inflammatory (De Melo, 2005; Sagnia et al., 2014), febrifuge, laxative and sudorific (Chopra et al. 1956; Nguyen et al., 1989), antiviral (Iberahim et al., 2007) used for liver disorders and convulsion as well as with antipyretic (Iqbal & Gnanaraj, 2011; Kirtikar & Basu, 1935; Pattanayak et al., 2017) properties.

Anatomic studies were carried out on *E. indica* previously (Babu et al., 2014; Rubina et al., 2007; Hafliger & Schoz, 1981; Bibi et al., 2007; Metcalfe, 1961; Metcalfe & Clioord, 1968; Kumar & Nautiyal, 2017; Saw, 2011). Numerous reports on foliar anatomy and micro morphology are used for delimiting the different groups or tribes in the Poaceae family (Brown, 1958; Ellis, 1986; Amarasinghe & Watson, 1990; Ahmad et al., 2011a).

Epidermal cells, stomata and hairs in dermal tissue system have already established to be important tools in delimitation of taxa in many plant families (Gajendera et al., 2009; Lackey, 1978; Stenglein et al., 2003). Anatomical features of leaf can help to explain taxonomic relationships at different levels (Metcalfe, 1960; Davila & Clark, 1990; Cai & Wang, 1994) and these leaf anatomical characters are of great value in grass systematic and characterization of broad groups within the grasses, particularly subfamilies and tribes. Sclerenchyma and bundle sheath (kranz sheath) amount, sclerenchyma width, leaf indumentums and length and frequency of epidermal cell are important features that can identify relationships among the genera of Poaceae (Dube & Morisset, 1987; Jarves & Barkworth, 1992; Yousaf et al., 2008). The leaf thickness, number and arrangement of vascular bundles might be systematically useful and the distribution of prickles may be relatively stable or environmentally variable (Ellis, 1986). The position of vascular bundles in the blades appears to be a useful diagnostic character above the generic level (Ellis, 1976). As an example, grasses in tribe Eragrostideae look morphologically similar but there is confusion observed in the discrimination of species, genera and the tribe on basis of morphological description. To resolve the taxonomic problems within the tribe, anatomical studies could be an important tool. Therefore, the aim of the present study is to identify and explore the leaf blade anatomically in *E. indica* that might prove to be helpful in the identification and differentiation at specific and generic levels. This study also helps to identify kranz features in plants that will be exposed plant as C₄ plant.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eleusine indica L. plants grown naturally in the field were collected from the inferior dry land of Barind region (Fig. 1). Healthy whole plants with stems, leaves and roots were brought to Crop Botany laboratory of EXIM Bank Agricultural University Bangladesh, Chapainawabganj. The research procedures were followed by Rahman & Sultana (2019; 2020) and Sultana (2020). The whole leaves were separated and washed under running tap water to remove dirt and soil. The transverse sections were prepared from leaf blade by cutting thin with stainless steel razor blade with hand with the help of a potato block and all sections were placed into water in a petri dish. Peel of leaf was used to observed stomata at upper and lower surface. Thin and uniform transverse sections of leaf blade and peel of leaf were isolated and kept into 1% (w/v) safranin solution for a period of 4-5 minutes and rinsed with distilled water for 1 minutes for three times to remove stain. The stained sections and peel were placed on fresh glass slide and mounted with a clean cover slip by putting few drops of glycerin and then observed under light microscope. The photographs were taken with digital camera and different types of cells were undertaken to measure in diameter. Ten cells for each type

Fig. 1 Photographs of *Eleusine indica* L. A) Growing plants in field condition. B) A plant containing root, stem and leaf. LB, Leaf blade; S, Stem; R, Root.

from ten sections were used to measure cells diameter and stomata number and its diameter. Numbers of stomata were counted from a square unit ($200 \mu\text{m}^2$).

3. RESULTS

Leaf veins were divided into three types: large longitudinal, small longitudinal and transverse veins in *Eleusine indica* L. (Fig. 2A). The adjacent point of leaf blade and leaf sheath is defined as ligule where long ligule hairs were present (Fig. 2B). Both upper and lower epidermises were composed of one-layered with oval and dumbbell shaped cells. The adaxial side (upper surface) features wide rounded ribs, separated by shallow V-shaped furrows (Fig. 3B).

Fig. 2 Photographs of leaf blade surface of *Eleusine indica* L. A) Leaf blade surface showing vein. B) Photographs of leaf with ligule hair. LLV, Long longitudinal vein; SLV, Small longitudinal vein; TV, Transverse vein.

The bulliform cells (motor cells) associated with colorless cells were present in the furrows of the adaxial (upper) epidermis. They have both oval and circular shaped cells, they were present in narrow groups penetrating the mesophyll, between two consecutive vascular bundles. There are two types of bulliform cell found: small and large which were $85.68 \mu\text{m}$ and $31.02 \mu\text{m}$ in average diameter, respectively (Table 1). The oval small bulliform cells were present immediately near to large bulliform cells and they made a small cluster.

Table 1 Diameter of different cells of leaf blade in *Eleusine indica* L.

Different type of cells in plant	Cell diameter (μm) ($\bar{x} \pm \text{S.E.}$)
Bundle sheath cell	46.88 \pm 1.60
Mesophyll cell	40.49 \pm 1.22
Sclerenchyma cell	10.83 \pm 0.52
Stomata cell	22.39 \pm 0.32
Subsidiary cell	42.60 \pm 1.68
Xylem cell	17.60 \pm 2.22
Large bulliform cell	85.68 \pm 4.45
Small bulliform cell	31.02 \pm 1.85

S.E., Standard error.

Stomata were present in both abaxial (lower) and adaxial (upper) surfaces of the leaf; therefore, the leaves were of amphistomatic type. Gramineous type stomata were observed in *E. indica* L. (Fig. 3A). The size of the stomata was $22.39 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter (Table 1). The number of stomata in abaxial surface was observed 30mm^{-2} . The guard cells of stomata were dumbbell shaped. Each guard cell was surrounded by subsidiary cells with a diameter of $42.60 \mu\text{m}$ (Table 1). The epidermal cells were arranged in parallel rows for both surfaces, with sinuous anticlinal walls; the cells were short and long. The short cells were located intercostally. The long cells found between the veins, were elongated. Five rows of long cells were present in abaxial (upper) surface where cork cells and micro hair were subsisted (Fig. 2A).

Between the two epidermal layers, a chlorophyllous mesophyll layer was observed but it was not differentiated into palisade and spongy parenchyma. A layer of mesophyll cell is present surrounding the bundle sheath cell in ring like fashion (Fig. 3C). The other mesophyll cells were compactly arranged in the leaf blade of the plant under study. A few numbers of small intercellular spaces was found. The mesophyll cells were $40.49 \mu\text{m}$ in average diameter (Table 1). Two mesophyll cells were present between two vascular bundles. The amount of chloroplast was higher in ring like fashion mesophyll cell (Fig. 3C).

The average diameter of bundle sheath cell was $46.88 \mu\text{m}$ shown in Table 1. Bundle sheath cells possessed chloroplasts. The number of chloroplast was higher in bundle sheath cells than mesophyll cells. Bundle sheath cells were observed surround vascular bundle (Fig. 4B).

Fig. 3 Photographs of leaf blade anatomy of *Eleusine indica* L. A) Epidermal view of leaf blade. B) Transverse section of a leaf blade showing vascular bundles arrangement. C) A closed up transverse view of a leaf blade within two vascular bundles. St, Stomata; LC, Long cell; SC, Short cell; Mh, Micro hair; SW, Sinuous wall; Pr, Prickle; Cc, Cork cell; Cz, Costal zone; LV, Large vascular bundle; SV, Short vascular bundle; CVB, Central vascular bundle; Bc, Bulliform cell; BS, Bundle sheath; Me, Mesophyll cell; Ph, Phloem; Xy, Xylem; MS, Mestome sheath; SC, Sclerenchyma, SG, Starch granule; Scc, Schelerenchyma cell, Rlf, Ring like fashion; Tc, Thick cuticle.

Sclerenchyma cells shown at the lower and upper sides of the vascular bundle (Fig. 3C) are present in small clusters. The size of the sclerenchyma cells was $6.67 \mu\text{m}$ in average diameter (Table 1). Sclerenchyma at large vascular bundles attached to bundle sheath. On the other hand, sclerenchyma at small vascular bundles present far from bundle sheath.

Two types of vascular bundle depending on size were observed in leaf blade of *E. indica* L. Some are large and some small in size. Central vascular bundle is similar to large vascular bundle. Large bundles were attended alternately with small bundles. The vascular bundles of the leaf blade were associated with strands of hypodermal

sclerenchyma. The vascular bundles were of the closed collateral conjoint type. The chlorenchymatous mesophyll cells were surrounded radially at vascular bundle. The xylem is found towards the upper side and the phloem towards the lower side. The xylem is composed of vessel elements (meta xylem), fibers and xylem parenchyma. Although fiber and xylem parenchyma were not detected clearly, the meta and proto xylem were found in the large vascular bundle. The phloem is made up of sieve tube elements, companion cells and phloem parenchyma. The phloem portion was clearly detectable but phloem elements were not separately identified. Thickened walls of mestome sheath were present around the xylem and phloem always in small and large bundle sheath (Fig. 3C). Xylem and phloem were present in the same radius where cambium was absent (Fig. 3C). The size of the xylem cells was 17.60µm in average diameter (Table 1). The vascular bundles were closed to each other due to the presence of two mesophyll cells. The shape of midrib was estimated more or less conical towards the direction of abaxial. A central large vascular bundle is present next to few small vascular bundles that stayed in touch of abaxial epidermis (Fig. 3C). The central region of the midrib showed colourless thin-walled large round shaped cells (Fig. 3C).

4. DISCUSSION

Leaf veins were divided into three types: large longitudinal veins, small longitudinal veins and transverse veins in *Eleusine indica* L. The achievement was similar to research of Chonan et al. (1974). In contrast, the two types of longitudinal vein were distinguished by diameter in paradermal view under the light microscope (Uneo et al., 2006). The present study revealed that microhairs features of the leaf surfaces have a considerable identifying characteristic of *E. indica* L. Friere et al. (2005) reported that *E. indica* L. is characterized by pear-like microhairs. However, Bibi et al. (2007) and Ahmad et al. (2011b) did not find microhairs instead found saddle-shaped silica bodies. The epidermal features of leaf can help elucidate taxonomic problems (Palmer & Tucker, 1981; Palmer et al., 1985; Davila & Clark 1990; Cai & Wang, 1994; Sanchez, 1974). These leaf epidermal characters are of great value in grass systematics and characterization of broader groups within the grasses, particularly subfamilies and tribes. According to Prat (1936), the types of microhairs and silica bodies are highly useful in systematic studies. A large- and two small-sized bulliform cells arranged a cluster that is a potential characteristic of this plant studied. It is help to survive the plant in the harsh conditions. Large bulliform cluster with large bulliform cells were reported to be in Cogon grass (Sima et al., 2017).

In leaf rolling for avoiding water loss in drought stress, bulliform cells play a vital role (Alvarez et al., 2008; Balsamo et al., 2006; Abernethy et al., 1998). Enlarged bulliform cells are a significant adaptation against water loss under drought condition. *Axonopus* spp. shows extensive leaf rolling during summer season (Arton 1986). This trend

was similar to the observation in Cogon grass (Hameed & Ashraf, 2009).

In the present study, two mesophyll cells were present between two vascular bundles, therefore, vascular bundles were closely arranged in the leaf blades of *E. indica* L. Interveneal distance is shorter in C₄ grasses (Dangler et al., 1994).

In the present study, two types of vascular bundle are present: large and small in size. The contrast result of the present observation was observed in Cogon grass where three types vascular bundle was observed (Sima et al., 2017). Three types vascular bundle have also been reported by Artschwager (1925) and Ellis (1976). The meta and proto xylem were found in the large vascular bundle. The existence of xylem elements in extra-large and large vascular bundle was revealed in Cogon grass (Sima et al., 2017). The phloem portion was clearly detectable but phloem elements were not separately identified in the studied plant. The phloem elements like sieve tube and companion cells were identified in sugarcane and it was nutrient transporting tissue (Colbert & Evert, 1982). Central vascular bundle in the midrib was surrounded by bundle sheath cells like other vascular bundle in leaf blade of experimented plant. This phenomenon of central vascular bundle in Cogon grass was dissimilar where they obtained vascular bundle surrounded by schelerenchyma (Sima et al., 2017). Thickened walls of mestome sheath were present around the xylem and phloem always in small and large bundle sheath. Mestome sheath in small bundles showed lacking, has been reported in many grasses (Carolin et al., 1973; Crookston & Moss, 1973; Brown, 1975; Colbert & Evert, 1982). Thickly walled mestome sheath was present around the phloem and partly of the xylem (Sima et al., 2017). Some large sized cells were round with thin wall located at the central region of the midrib. The similar result was reported in sugarcane (Colbert & Evert, 1982) and in Cogon grass (Sima et al., 2017).

4. CONCLUSION

Poaceae is one of the largest families among the angiosperms, and is represented in every phytogeographic region in the world. The leaf epidermal features of leaf blade i.e. epidermal cells, stomata, prickles and hairs in the experimented plant provide extensive taxonomic data relating grasses. Bundle sheath, the width of sclerenchyma, mesophyll cell number within vascular bundle and mesophyll cell arrangement in ring like fashion are features of C₄ plant revealed in the experimented plant *Eleusine indica* L.

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